

A detail from a painting showing two hands resting on a piece of fabric. The fabric is a light blue or teal color with a wide, intricate white lace-like border. The hands are positioned as if holding or adjusting the fabric. The background is dark and indistinct.

AMBROSIVS MARTINENGVS. EPISCOPVS BERGOMENSIS, RELIGIONE
ET DOCTRINA CELEBRIS. QVI CVM PER XXXX ANNOS SVAM
ECCLESIAM SANCTISSIME GVBERNASSET, VETEREM PRECLARE VIRTVTIS
ET FAMILIÆ FAMAM, NOVIS LAVDIBVS INSIGNITER CVMVLAVIT. ANNO. DNI. M. LV.